

Structures and deformation phases affecting the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt south of Téra (Liptako, West Niger, and West African Craton)

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(02), 952-961

Publication history: Received on 23 June 2024; revised on 04 August 2024; accepted on 07 August 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.2.2402>

Abstract

The present study focuses on the geological formations of the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt of southern Téra in the Niger Liptako (NE portion of the Man Shield of the West African Craton). The main objective of this study is to characterize the deformation phases that affected the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt to the south of Téra. The methodology implemented is based on a structural analysis using field data. These formations are affected by two major deformation phases, D1 and D2. Phase D1 comprises three episodes: D1a, D1b and D1c. The first episode (D1a) developed the S1 cleavage (NE-SW). This episode is linked to a NW-SE shortening (N130°). The second episode (D1b) is marked by S2 crenulation cleavage, micro-folding and the dextral reactivation of N45° shear zones. This episode is linked to an E-W shortening. The third episode (D1c) is highlighted by the NW-SE S3 fracture cleavage and the sinistral reactivation of the N45° shear zones. A N-S to NNE-SSW shortening was obtained for episode D1c. Phase D2 is essentially brittle. It favoured the development of submeridian fractures and conjugate WNW-ESE (sinistral) and ENE-WSW (dextral) shear fractures. This deformation is compatible with a generally E-W direction of shortening.

Keywords: West African Craton; Deformation; Diagorou-Darbani; Liptako; Niger

1. Introduction

The Birimian formations, oriented broadly NE-SW, were deformed by the Eburnean polyphase thermo-tectonic event [1] between 2.16 and 1.98 Ga [2]–[8]. This event is divided into 2 to 4 major deformation phases, noted respectively: D1, D2, D3 and D4. These deformation phases generated several structural elements [9]–[14]. The first three phases (D1 to D3) are regional in character, unlike D4, which has only been recognised locally, particularly in the Liptako region of Niger [15], [16]. Phase D1 is the subject of debate. For some authors, it is associated with modern tangential collisional tectonics [2], [3], [5], [13], and for others, it is a question of vertical, archaic tectonics of the Archean type [9]–[11], [17], [18]. The deformation phases D2, D3 and D4 have been linked by some authors to the functioning of the major shear zones [2], [3], [12], [16], [19], [20].

Very little structural data has been published for the Niger Liptako. Structural studies carried out in the Liptako have mainly focused on the Sirba [21], Diagorou-Darbani [11], [16], Gorouol [22] and Makalondi [23] greenstone belts. Structural studies undertaken mainly in granitoid plutons are few and have concerned the Téra-Ayorou pluton [9], [17], [24], [25]. The aim of this study is to characterize the various deformation phases that affected the Birimian formations in the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt to the south of Téra and to determine the average directions of shortening.

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2. Geological context

The West African Craton consists of two Shield, the Reguibat Shield in the north and the Léo-Man Shield in the south, each comprising an Archean western province dated at 3.5 to 2.7 Ga [26], [27] and a Birimian eastern province dated at 2.27 to 1.96 Ga [20]. The Niger Liptako corresponds to the north-eastern (NE) edge of the Léo-Man Shield (Figure 1a). The Niger Liptako is characterized by alternating greenstone belts (Gorouol, Diagorou-Darbani, Sirba and Makalondi) and granitoid plutons (Téra-Ayorou, Dargol-Gothèye and Torodi) trending broadly NE-SW (Figure 1a). The greenstone belts consist of metabasalts with local pillow lavas, amphibolites, ultramafic to mafic plutonites often transformed into talcchists, talc-chloritoschists and chloritoschists, metamorphosed sediments and volcano-sediments, ranging from greenschist to amphibolite facies [16], [21]–[23], [28]–[39]. These belt rocks are intruded by granitic to dioritic plutons, sometimes associated with intermediate to acid volcanics [22], [29]. The granitoid plutons have an elongation direction sub-parallel to the major N45°E shear zones [11]. They are represented by granodiorites, tonalites and quartz diorites, locally gneissified at the contact with the host rock [9], [16], [17]. The U-Pb ages on zircon obtained from the plutons range from 2174 ± 4 Ma (Dargol pluton, [16]) to 2158 ± 9 Ma (Téra pluton, [40]). The Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt studied here is located in the central part of the Niger Liptako. It is divided into two branches with a mean strike N45°E, separated by the Taka pluton (Figure 1b). The western branch is predominantly magmatic, while the eastern branch is sedimentary and volcano-sedimentary (Figure 1b).

Figure 1 (a) Synthetic geological map of the Man Ridge modified from [41]; (b) Geological map of the Diagorou-Darbani Birim belt modified from [31].

3. Methodology

The methodology used for this study consisted of field and laboratory work. The field work consisted of surveys, petrographic description, structural measurements and sampling. The methodology used consisted of a structural analysis of the surrounding rocks in the field. This structural analysis involved identifying and describing the geological structures affecting the host rocks and pegmatites.

In the case of the host rocks, this involved structural measurements of foliation/cleavage, the presence of lineation, faults, shear or folding zones. In the laboratory, the various structural measurements collected in the field were automatically projected onto the SCHMIDT diagram (lower hemisphere) using the program (Stereonet 9, [42]). The resulting stereograms allow us to deduce the different average directions of shortening responsible for the different structures observed in the field. The laboratory work involved making thin sections and observing them under a

polarizing microscope, with a view to characterizing the tectonic microstructures. The study of cross-relationships between tectonic structures identified in outcrop and during microtectonic studies.

4. Results

The Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt has two deformation phases, D1 and D2. The first deformation phase, D1, is characterized by cleavage, micro-folding, boudinage and shear zones. This D1 phase comprises three episodes D1a (ductile to semi-ductile), D1b (semi-ductile) and D1c (semi-ductile to brittle). The second deformation phase D2, is brittle and post-Birimian.

4.1. Deformation phase D1

4.1.1. Episode D1a

The ductile to semi-ductile deformation episode is characterized by symmetrical cleavage/foliation (S1) running N35° to N55° (Figure 2a). This cleavage affects talcschists, micaschists and quartzites. The stereograms show an average shortening of N130° (Figure 2b).

Figure 2 (a) S1 foliation with orientation N25° to N45° observed in the talcschist; (b) S1 foliation, with stereogram showing the direction of shortening (N130°) of S1

4.1.2. Episode D1b

The D1a episode of ductile to semi-ductile deformation is followed by a second semi-ductile episode D1b. The D1b deformation is characterized by cleavage/foliation S2 in the axial plane direction N40° to N70°, microfolding, boudinage and dextral shear zones.

4.1.2.1. Microfolding

The cleavage/ foliation (S1) is often affected by an episode of P2 microfolding. Anisopach P2 microfolds with axes oriented N35° to N45° are generally observed in talcschists. The axes of these microfolds dip 10° to 30° to the NE. Exaggerated folding can sometimes lead to the development of axial plane or crenulation cleavage (S2), sub-parallel to the axial planes of the P2 microfolds (Figures 3a and b). The S2 cleavage trends between N40° and N°45 with dips varying from 65° to 85°, generally to the NW.

4.1.2.2. Dextral shear zones

The N45° to N70° dextral shear zones affecting the talcschist are responsible for the development of the S1/C mills. A shortening N70° to E-W has been obtained for these dextral shear zones (Figures 3c and d).

Figure 3 (a, b) Microfolding of S1 inducing a subparallel crenulation S2 cleavage in the axial planes of the microfolds; (c, d) S/C fabric with a dextral shearing component affecting the talcschist

4.1.3. Episode D1c

The semi-ductile to brittle D1c episode is associated with a cleavage of S3 fractures oriented N90° to N140° and S1/C fabrications, associated with the play of sinistral shear zones (Figure 4). A N20° shortening was obtained for the D1c episode.

Figure 4 Talcschist affected by three planes of cleavage: S1, S2 and S3

4.2. D2 deformation phase

This is an essentially brittle deformation phase. It is represented by submeridian fractures and conjugate WNW-ESE (sinistral) and ENE-WSW (dextral) thrusts. This strike-slip system is compatible with a generally E-W direction of shortening.

5. Discussion

In the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt, structural analysis indicates that there are at least two major deformation phases D1 and D2. The first deformation phase, D1, is characterized by cleavage, micro-folding, boudinage and shear zones. This D1 phase comprises three episodes D1a (ductile to semi-ductile), D1b (semi-ductile) and D1c (semi-ductile to brittle). The second deformation phase D2, is brittle and post-Birimian (Figure 5).

5.1. Eburnean deformation phase D1

5.1.1. Ductile to semi-ductile D1a episode

The D1a deformation episode is characterized by cleavage/foliation (S1). This episode has been linked to an average NW-SE shortening (N130°).

In the Niger Liptako, this D1a episode is comparable to the D1 phases of [24], [25] in the Téra-Ayorou pluton. In the Diagorou-Darbani belt, [11] highlighted a NW-SE regional shortening episode (D1a) similar to the D1a episode in the present study. This D1a episode is similar to the early episodes of the D2 deformation phase obtained by [16]. In the Gorouol belt, this D1a episode is similar to the D1a episode obtained by [22] and to the D1 phase of [43], [44]. This D1a episode is also comparable to the D1a episode obtained by [23] in the Makalondi belt. As shown by [9], [28], the

transcurrent episode of deformation (D1a) affecting the Niger Liptako around 2170 Ma could correspond to lateral accretion 'gluing' this domain to an eastern bloc. According to these authors, the D1a compression is also linked to a continuum of deformation and magmatic manifestations suggesting a diachronism of Eburnean deformation. This deformation continuum would be strongly influenced by the emplacement of large granitoid plutons and by the operation of regional shear zones [11], [16]. For [17], [11], the D1a episode is globally linked to the emplacement and swelling of large granitoid plutons.

At the scale of the West African Craton, the D1a episode obtained in the present study corresponds to the early deformation phase (D1) highlighted by [3] in Burkina Faso, which has been attributed to tangential tectonics. This D1a episode is also comparable to the D2 deformation phase described in Burkina Faso by [45] and to the D1 phase described by [46], [47]. In Senegal, this D1a episode is equivalent to the D1 deformation phase of [48]. The D1a episode highlighted by the present study corresponds in Mali to the D1 phase of [49]. This D1a episode coincides respectively with the Eburnean D1 and D2 deformation phases described by [49], [50] in the Siguiri greenstone belt in Guinea. In Ghana, a similar deformation phase (D3) was reported by [7].

5.1.2. Semi-ductile D1b episode

The D1b episode of ductile to semi-ductile deformation is characterized by the crenulation cleavage S2, micro-folding, boudinage and dextral shear channels responsible for the S1/C mills. This semi-ductile episode D1b has been linked to NW-SE shortening

In the Niger Liptako, this D1b episode is comparable to the D2 phase described by [16] and to the D1b episode described by [11] in the Diagorou-Darbani belt. It is also comparable to the D1b episodes described by [22], [23] in the Gorouol and Makalondi belts respectively. This episode is comparable to the D2 of [24] in the Téra-Ayorou pluton.

In the West African Craton, the D1b episode is comparable to the Eburnean D2 deformation phase defined in Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana [3], [4], [10], [19], [52]–[54].

5.1.3. Semi-ductile to brittle D1c episode

The semi-ductile to brittle D1c episode is associated with fractures and fracture cleavage S3 N90° to N120° and sinistral shear zones. It affects all the previous formations. This compressive episode is characterized by an NNE-SSW to NE-SE shortening direction.

In the Niger Liptako, this D1c episode is comparable to the D2 obtained by [19] and the D1c episode of [22] in the Gorouol belt. In the Diagorou-Darbani belt, this D1c episode is similar to the D3 of [16] and to the D1c episode obtained and the D2 described by [11]. The D1a episode is similar to the D1c of [23] obtained in the Makalondi belt. At the scale of the West African Craton, this D1c episode is comparable to the D3 revealed in Burkina-Faso [3] and Ivory Coast [54].

5.2. Post-Eburnean deformation phase D2

The D2 deformation phase is characterized by conjugate dextral and sinistral shear fractures. This D2 deformation phase is comparable to the D2 phases of [23], [25] in the Makalondi belt and the Téra-Ayorou pluton respectively.

Figure 5 Schematic model of the different deformation phases affecting the formations of the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt south of Téra

6. Conclusion

The geological formations of the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt in southern Téra are affected by two major deformation phases, D1 and D2.

Phase D1 comprises three episodes: D1a, D1b and D1c. The first episode (D1a) developed the S1 cleavage (NE-SW). This episode is linked to a NW-SE shortening (N130°). The second episode (D1b) is marked by S2 crenulation cleavage, micro-folding and the dextral reactivation of N45° shear zones. This episode is linked to an E-W shortening. The third episode (D1c) is highlighted by the NW-SE S3 fracture cleavage and the sinistral reactivation of the N45° shear zones. A N-S to NNE-SSW shortening was obtained for episode D1c. Phase D2 is essentially brittle. It favored the development of submeridian fractures and conjugate WNW-ESE (sinistral) and ENE-WSW (dextral) shear fractures. This deformation is compatible with a generally E-W direction of shortening.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Références

- [1] Bonhomme M. Contribution to the geochronological study of the West African Platform. Ann Fac Sci Univ Clermont-Ferrand Géol Minéral. 1962 ;5(62).
- [2] Feybesse JL, Billa M, Guerrot C, Duguey E, Lescuyer JL, Milési JP, et al. The Paleoproterozoic Ghanaian province: Geodynamic model and ore controls, including regional stress modeling. Precambrian Res. 2006 ;149(3-4) :149-96.

- [3] Baratoux L, Metelka V, Naba S, Jessell MW, Grégoire M, Ganne J. Juvenile Paleoproterozoic crust evolution during the Eburnean orogeny (2.2–2.0 Ga), western Burkina Faso. *Precambrian Res.* 2011;191(1-2):18-45.
- [4] Jessell MW, Amponsah PO, Baratoux L, Asiedu DK, Loh GK, Ganne J. Crustal-scale transcurrent shearing in the Paleoproterozoic Sefwi-Sunyani-Comoé region, West Africa. 2012;212-213:155-68.
- [5] Perrouty S, Aillères L, Jessell MW, Baratoux L, Bourassa Y, Crawford. Revised Eburnean geodynamic evolution of the gold-rich southern Ashanti Belt, Ghana, with new field and geophysical evidence of pre-Tarkwaian deformations. *Precambrian Res.* 2012 ;204(205) :12-39.
- [6] Block S, Jessell MW, Aillères L, Baratoux L, Bruguier O, Zeh A, et al. Lower crust exhumation during Paleoproterozoic (Eburnean) orogeny, NW Ghana, West African Craton: interplay of coeval contractional deformation and extensional gravitational collapse. *Precambrian Res.* 2016a ;274 :82-109.
- [7] Block S, Baratoux L, Zeh A, Laurent O, Bruguier O, Jessell MW, et al. Paleoproterozoic juvenile crust formation and stabilisation in the south-eastern West African Craton (Ghana); New insights from UPb-Hf zircon data and geochemistry. *Precambrian Res.* 2016b ;287 :1-30.
- [8] Masurel Q, Thébaud N, Miller JM, Ulrich S. The tectono-magmatic framework to gold mineralisation in the Sadiola-Yatela gold camp and implications for the paleotectonic setting of the Kédougou-Kéniéba inlier, West Africa. *Precambrian Res.* 2017; 292:35-56.
- [9] Pons J, Barbey P, Dupuis D, Leger JM. Mechanisms of pluton emplacement and structural evolution of a 2.1 Ga juvenile continental crust: the Birimian of southwestern Niger. *Precambrian Res.* 1995 ;70 :281-301.
- [10] Vidal M, Delor C, Pouclet A, Simeon Y, Alric G. Geodynamic evolution of Africa between 2.2 and 2 Ga: the 'Archean' style of the green belts and birimian sedimentary assemblages of north-eastern Côte d'Ivoire. *Bull Société Géologique Fr.* 1996 ;167(3) :307-19.
- [11] Soumaila A, Konate M. Characterisation of deformation in the Diagorou-Darbani Birimian belt (Palaeoproterozoic) (Niger Liptako, West Africa). *Afr Geo Revue.* 2005 ;13(3) :161-78.
- [12] Hein KA. Succession of structural events in the Goren greenstone belt (Burkina Faso): Implications for West African tectonics. *J Afr Earth Sci.* 2010 ;56(2-3):83-94.
- [13] de Kock GS, Théveniaut H, Botha PMW, Gyapong W. Timing the structural events in the Palaeoproterozoic Bolé–Nangodi belt terrane and adjacent Maluwe basin, West African craton, in central-west Ghana. *J Afr Earth Sci.* 2012; 65:1-24.
- [14] Block S, Ganne J, Baratoux L, Zeh A, Parra-Avila LA, Jessell MW, et al. Petrological and geochronological constraints on lower crust exhumation during Paleoproterozoic (Eburnean) orogeny, NW Ghana, West African Craton. *J Metamorph Geol.* 2015 ;33 :463-94.
- [15] Abdou A, Bonnot H, Bory Kadey D, Chalamet D, Saint Martin M, Younfa I. Explanatory notes for the 1:100,000 and 1:200,000 geological maps of Liptako. *Ministère Mines Géologie Rep Niger.* 1998 ;64.
- [16] Soumaila A. Structural, petrographic and geochemical study of the Diagorou-Darbani Liptako birimian belt, western Niger (West Africa) [Franche-Comté University PhD Thesis]. 2000.
- [17] Dupuis D, Pons J, Prost AE. Plutonic emplacement and Birimian deformation in western Niger. *Comptes Rendus Académie Sci Paris.* 1991 ;312 :769-76.
- [18] Lompo M. Geological and structural study of the Birimian series in the Kwademen region, Burkina Faso, West Africa [Blaise Pascal University Thesis]. 1991.
- [19] Tshibubudze A, Hein KA, Marquis P. The Markoye shear zone in NE Burkina Faso. *J Afr Earth Sci.* 2009; 55:245-56.
- [20] Grenholm M. The global tectonic context of the ca. 2.27-1.96 Ga Birimian Orogen—Insights from comparative studies, with implications for supercontinent cycles. *Earth-Sci Rev.* 2019;
- [21] Ama Salah I. Petrography and structural relationships of the metavolcanic and sedimentary formations of the Birimian of western Niger, Problem of crustal accretion in the Lower Proterozoic [PhD Thesis]. University of Orléans; 1991.
- [22] Hallarou MM. Context of copper and molybdenum mineralisation in the Birimian formations of the Kourki region (Liptako, West Niger) : Genesis and Magmatic Evolution [PhD Thesis]. Abdou Moumouni University of Niamey ; 2021.

- [23] Garba Saley H. Context of the emplacement of chromium and copper mineralisation in the birimian formations of the Makalondi region (Liptako, western Niger): geodynamic implications [PhD Thesis]. [Niger] : Abdou Moumouni University of Niamey ; 2022.
- [24] Ahmed YL, Attourabi SA, Hallarou MM, Chamsi LI, Noura GR, Chékaraou MMS. Relationship between regional deformation and the emplacement of the Dibilo pegmatites (Liptako, West Niger). *J Afr Earth Sci.* 2022 ;198(104814) :1-16.
- [25] Noura GR, Ahmed Y, Hallarou MM, Maharou HI, Attourabi SA, Garba Saley H. Structural characteristics of the granitoids in the Ayorou and Kandadji area (Liptako, western Niger). *Int J Innov Appl Stud.* 2023b ;40(4) :1423-36.
- [26] Kouamelan AN, Peucat JJ, Delor C. Archean relics (3.5 Ga) within birimian magmatism (2.1 Ga) from Côte d'Ivoire, West African craton. *Comptes Rendus Académie Sci* 324. 1997 ;2 :719-27.
- [27] Potrel A, Peucat JJ, Faning CM. Archean crustal evolution of the West African Craton: example of the Amsaga Area (Reguibat Rise). U-Pb and Sm-Nd evidence for crustal growth and recycling. *Precambrian Res.* 1998 ;90 :107-17.
- [28] Ama Salah I, Liegeois JP, Pouclet A. Evolution of an early Birimian oceanic island arc in the Nigerian Liptako (Sirba): geology, geochronology and geochemistry. *J Afr Sci.* 1996 ;22(3) :235-54.
- [29] Soumaila A, Henry P, Rossy M. Context of emplacement of the basic rocks of the Diagorou-Darbani birimian greenstone belt (Liptako, Niger, West Africa): oceanic plateau or arc environment/back-arc oceanic basin. *C R Geosci N° 336.* 2004 ;1137-47.
- [30] Soumaila A, Garba Z. Metamorphism of the Diagorou-Darbani (Liptako, Niger, West Africa) Birimian greenstone belt (Palaeoproterozoic) formations. *Afr Geosci Rev.* 2006 ;13(1) :107-28.
- [31] Soumaila A, Henry P, Garba Z, Rossi M. REE patterns, Nd-Sm and U-Pb ages of the metamorphic rocks of the Diagorou-Darbani greenstone belt (Liptako, SW Niger): implication for Birimian (Palaeoproterozoic) crustal genesis. *Geol Soc Lond Spec Publ.* 2008 ;19-32.
- [32] Soumaila A, Garba Z, Moussa IA, Nouhou H, Sebag D. Highlighting the root of a paleoproterozoic oceanic arc in Liptako, Niger, West Africa. *J Geol Min Res.* 2016a ;8(2):13-27.
- [33] Soumaila A, Ahmed YL, Nouhou H. Geochemistry of Ladanka basites and ultrabasites (Liptako, Niger). *JSci.* 2016b ;16(3):37-54.
- [34] Garba Saley H, Konate M, Ahmed YL, Soumaila A. Manganese mineralisation in North Téra (Liptako, western Niger): origin and conditions of emplacement. *REV CAMES Sci Vie Terre Agron.* 2017 ;5(2) :2424-7235.
- [35] Garba Saley H, Soumaila A, Konate M. Alteration Processes of Paleoproterozoic Manganese Protores of the North Téra: Mineralogy and Geochemistry (West Africa). *J Geol Resour Eng.* 2018; 6:177-93.
- [36] Hallarou MM, Konate M, Olatunji AS, Ahmed YL. The Paleoproterozoic porphyry copper-molybdenum deposit of Kourki (Liptako Province, Western Niger). *Geol Soc Lond Spec Publ.* 2020 ;32pp.
- [37] Hallarou MM, Konate M, Olatunji AS, Ahmed YL, Ajayi FF, Abdul RM. Re-Os Ages for the Kourki Porphyry Cu-Mo Deposits, North West Niger (West Africa): Geodynamic Implications. *Eur J Environ Earth Sci.* 2020 ;1(4) :13pp.
- [38] Garba Saley H, Konate M, Soumaila A. Textural study of the paleoproterozoic chromitites of the Makalondi Region (nigerien Liptako province, Western Niger): origin and condition of emplacement. *Afr Sci.* 2021 ;18(1) :186-202.
- [39] Hallarou MM, Konate M, Ahmed YL, Chékaraou MMS, Attourabi SA, Chamsi LI, et al. Paleoproterozoic basaltic rocks related to plumes in the Gorouol belt (Liptako West Niger). *Int J Sci Eng Appl Sci IJSEAS.* 2022 ;8(3) :66-73.
- [40] Cheilletz A, Babey P, Lama C, Pons J, Zimmermann JL, Dautel D. Cooling age of the West African juvenile Birimian crust, U/Pb and K-Ar data from the 2.1Ga formations of SW Niger. *Comptes Rendus Académie Sci Paris Sér II.* 1994 ;319 :435-42.
- [41] Milési JP, Feybesse JL, Ledru P, Dommangeat A, Ouedraogo MF, Marcoux E, et al. Gold mineralisation in West Africa. Their relationship with lithostructural evolution in the Lower Proterozoic. *Chron Rech Minière N° 497.* 1989 ;3-98.
- [42] Allmendinger RW. Stereonet 9, version 9.5.3 based on the Allmendinger, R. W., Cardozo, N. C., and Fisher, D., 2013, *Structural Geology Algorithms: Vectors & Tensors*: Cambridge, England, Cambridge University Press, 289 pp. 2016;

- [43] Tshibubudze A, Hein KA, Peters LFH, Woolfe AJ, McCuaig TC. Oldest U-Pb crystallisation age for the West African Craton from the Oudalan-Gorouol belt of Burkina Faso. *Geol Soc South Afr.* 2013 ;169-81.
- [44] Tshibubudze A, Hein KA, McCuaig TC. The relative and absolute chronology of strato-tectonic events in the Gorom-Gorom granitoid terrane and Oudalan-Gorouol belt, northeast Burkina Faso. *J Afr Earth Sci.* 2015 ;37.
- [45] McCuaig TC, Fougereuse D, Salvi S, Siebenaller L, Parra-Avila LA, Seed R, et al. The Inata deposit, Belahouro District, northern Burkina Faso. *Ore Geol Rev.* 2016; 78:639-44.
- [46] Naba S, Lompo M, Debat P, Bouchez JL, Béziat D. Structure and emplacement model for late-orogenic Paleoproterozoic granitoids: the Tenkodogo–Yamba elongate pluton (Eastern Burkina Faso). *J Afr Earth Sci.* 2004;38(1):41-57.
- [47] Vegas N, Naba S, Bouchez JL, Jessell MW. Structure and emplacement of granite plutons in the Paleoproterozoic crust of Eastern Burkina Faso: rheological implications. *Int J Earth Sci Geol Rundsch.* 2008 ;97 :1165-80.
- [48] Delor C, Couëffé R, Goujou JC, Diallo DP, Théveniaut H, Fullgraf T, et al. Explanatory note for the 1:200,000 geological map of Senegal, Saraya-Kédougou East sheet. *Ministère Mines L’Industrie L’Agro-Ind PME Dir Mines Géologie Dakar.* 2010 ;
- [49] Miller JM, Davis J, Baratoux L, McCuaig TC, Metelka V, Jessell MW. Evolution of gold systems in Guinea, southern Mali and western Burkina Faso. *AMIRA Int Ltd P934A-West Afr Explor Initiat-Stage 2 Final Unpubl Rep Append D1.* 2014;127-234.
- [50] Salvi S, Velásquez G, Miller JM, Béziat D, Siebenaller L, Bourassa Y. The Pampe gold deposit (Ghana): Constraints on sulfide evolution during gold mineralization. *Ore Geol Rev.* 2016 ;78 :673-86.
- [51] Lebrun E, Miller JM, Thébaud N, Ulrich S, Campbell McCuaig T. Structural Controls on an Orogenic Gold System: The World-Class Siguiri Gold District, Siguiri Basin, Guinea, West Africa. *Soc Econ Geol Inc Econ Geol.* 2017; 112:73-98.
- [52] Ledru P, Pons J, Milési JP, Feybesse JL, Johan V. Transcurrent tectonics and polycyclic evolution in the lower Proterozoic of Senegal-Mali. *Precambrian Res.* 1991; 50:337-54.
- [53] McFarlane H, Aillères L, Betts P, Ganne J, Baratoux L, Jessell MW. Nascent Palaeoproterozoic episodic collisional orogenesis: the Eburnean Orogeny of the West African Craton. *Oral Present Rodinia 2017 Townsv Aust Geol Soc Aust Abstr.* 2017 ;121 :73-4.
- [54] Jean Marie Pria KK, Coulibaly Y, Houssou NN, Ephrem Allialy M, Dimitri Boya TKL, Tayebi M, et al. Structures, Deformation Mechanisms and Tectonic Phases, Recorded in Paleoproterozoic Granitoids of West African Craton, Southern Part: Example of Kan’s Complex (Central of Côte d’Ivoire). *Eur Sci J.* 2019 ;15(18) :1857-7881.